

Challenges for Improving Nursing Documentation at PHCs, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia

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Abstract

Background: Family and Community Medicine Department is providing quality primary health care service through its 16 peripherals PHCs that are providing direct patients care and performing documentation on patients' charts on electronic nursing records (Rabet system). Each of these peripherals is taking a sample of 10% of their total patient census per session, subject to submission every Sunday of the week for audit for compliance to completeness. Nursing documentation is a legal record and communication for continuity of care; it is an important function of professional nursing practice. The project aimed to examine the current practice of nursing documentation and develop a project for improvement. The project was conducted from January to July 2024. It is based on the fundamental concepts of assessment and documentation.

Methods: Nursing documentation uses electronic nursing records (Rabet system) in entering data for each patient and this is the documentation-guiding framework. In this initiative, we approached the problem by multiple interventions. The memo released by the Director of Nursing dated August 02, 2023, asking all the staff nurses to follow strict compliance to documentation completeness criteria in order to improve documentation practice. An audit was continuously conducted weekly from January up to July 2024, followed by a monthly meeting to all Head Nurses citing the full adherence of each staff. Per peripherals there are two staff nurses who are covering the screening area for documentation and with 16 peripherals; two of these peripherals are having 24hrs duty (6 sessions), while the other peripherals they are having regular 3 sessions. Verbal counseling to those staff who are neglecting to complete the documentation process. The nursing documentation completion rates before the implementation of the action plan /intervention were compared with the completion rates after the implementation. The increase in nursing documentation completion rates in post-intervention implementation was attributed to the effectiveness of the intervention.

Results: The nursing documentation completion rates during the months when the action plan was still being developed were notably low, with January 2024 at 51%, February at 65%, and March at 81%. After the implementation of the intervention strategy, the completion rates improved, reaching 90% in April 2024, 91% in May and June, and 96% in July 2024. This demonstrates the effectiveness of the intervention implementation in improving nursing documentation compliance.

Conclusion: The nursing Documentation Completeness Project had a significant impact on improving the completion rate of nursing documentation. The goal of the project is to guarantee that patient information is regularly and accurately captured by standardizing and

More Information

How to cite this article: Al Hajla T, Domingo L, Al Otaibi S, Al Mutairi S, Buelva JL, Al Rashedi A, Al Otaibi M, Alotaibi A, Maher M, Kofi M. Challenges for Improving Nursing Documentation at PHCs, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. *Eur J Med Health Res*, 2024;2(5):303-8.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2024.2(5).33

Keywords:

Nursing Documentation,
Primary Health Care,
Quality Improvement.

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optimizing nursing documentation procedures. This project enhances clinical decision-making, lowers the risk of errors, fosters continuity of care, and increases communication between medical personnel.

Recommendations: Adopting the Nursing Documentation Completeness Project is suggested as an essential strategy for improving the standard of nursing documentation completeness for effective patient care.

Introduction

Nursing documentation is vital in the provision of quality patient care [1]. It is crucial in ensuring that ethical standards are being upheld in healthcare settings [2] and in providing clear communication among health care professionals to prevent medical errors [3]. It also supports the monitoring of the outcomes of patient care and in the identification of patterns that enable informed decisions and the adjustment of treatment plans for effective patient management [4]. Additionally, complete patient records must be kept up to date for healthcare facilities to meet accreditation and regulatory requirements [5]. For audits, inspections, and certification maintenance, proper documentation is necessary. In summary, nursing documentation is vital for the preservation of legal, ethical, and professional standards in healthcare, the enhancement of patient outcomes, and the guarantee of secure and efficient operations in clinical environments.

The significance of nursing documentation is widely acknowledged, yet it has been observed that this critical component of patient management is often overlooked. Despite its recognized role in ensuring effective communication, legal protection, and in patient safety, it is frequently disregarded [6]. Errors in timely and complete documentation still happen in many healthcare settings, even though it is known to play a vital role in guaranteeing efficient communication, legal protection, and patient safety [7]. Research has indicated that poor documentation procedures include lack of awareness or appropriate training, excessive workloads, and time constraints [8]. The necessity for higher attention on effective documentation processes in healthcare institutions is highlighted by the potential consequences of neglect, which include misunderstanding, an increase in medical errors, and impaired patient outcomes [9]. This unnecessary neglect may lead to miscommunication, increased medical errors, and compromised patient outcomes, highlighting the need for stronger emphasis on proper documentation protocols in healthcare institutions.

In healthcare settings in Saudi Arabia, challenges in patient care include a shortage of nurses considering the high volume of patients being provided with medical attention as well as heavy workloads [10]. These factors contribute to inconsistent quality of patient care [11, 12] and one of the significant effect of these challenges in nursing practice is difficulty in

maintaining timely documentation of patient records [13,14]. Effective and efficient record-keeping is vital for patient safety and care continuity. However, when nurses are overburdened, documentation of patient data is affected. These issues can be addressed by improvements in nurse-patient ratios, management of workloads, and support system for documentation processes. The use of technology has been shown to improve accurate and timely documentation and accessibility to patient data. However, it requires proper implementation and training to be fully effective.

In Riyadh, Family and Community Medicine provides primary health care services through its 16 peripherals. Direct patient care and documentation on patients' chart are supported by electronic nursing System (RABET). Each of these peripherals takes a 10% sample from the total patient's census per session and submitted at the end of the week for audit in terms of compliance to completeness. Nursing documentation serves as both a legal record and a communication tool essential for continuity of care. However, nurses were faced with a challenge in navigating the new system of patient data documentation which led to low completion. The management issued a memorandum in 2023 strongly urging the nurses to complete documentation of patient data. In response, an intervention was implemented to address the concern and ensure compliance. The intervention focused on improving accuracy and timeliness of patient record-keeping, which is vital for maintaining high quality patient care, enhance patient safety, and facilitate clear communication among healthcare professionals. As a vital component of professional nursing practice, improving nursing documentation is crucial for enhancing patient care; thus, research in this area is highly significant.

The objective of the study is to evaluate the impact of an intervention coined, *Nursing Documentation Completeness Project* on the rate of completion of nursing documentation. The completion rates during the pre-and post- implementation of the intervention strategy were compared to assess its effectiveness.

Methods

Study Objectives

The aim of the study is to evaluate the effectiveness of CNDII as an intervention strategy in addressing low nursing documentation. The objectives are:

- a. determine the nursing documentation completion rates before and after the implementation of the intervention; and
- b. compare the documentation completion rates before and after the implementation of the intervention

Study Setting

The study was conducted at the Family and Community Medicine Department of Prince Sultan Military Medical City, which oversees 16 Primary Health Care Facilities.

These centers are staffed by six head nurses and 16 charge nurses, who manage operations across all 16 locations. The patient volume varies, with the larger PHC centers handling approximately 200 to 300 patients daily, while the smaller peripheral centers serve around 50 to 100 patients each day. This high patient load highlights the critical need for efficient nursing documentation to ensure quality care and streamline healthcare delivery across the 16 PHC centers.

Figure 1: Study Design

Study Implementation

1. Assessment and Diagnosis

The issue of incomplete nursing documentation came to the forefront upon issuance of a memorandum from the Nursing Administration mandating 100% compliance with the documentation process using the RABET system. This directive highlighted the critical need for accurate and timely documentation to ensure quality health care, legal accountability, and facilitate clear communication among healthcare teams. The RABET system targets standard nursing documentation for quality recording and reducing errors, making full compliance integral in maintaining operational efficiencies and patient safety while seeking health care

from the health facilities. The initial interview with the nurses on the reasons why they were unable to complete nursing documentation included unfamiliarity with the new system of nursing documentation and the large volume of patients considering the few nurses available to handle them. These were considered in planning and designing an intervention strategy.

2. Planning Strategy and Development of an Intervention Strategy

The intervention strategy which was developed was coined Nursing Documentation Completeness Project. The elements of this intervention strategy are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: intervention strategy which was developed was coined Nursing Documentation Completeness Project

Objective	Strategy	In-charge	Timeline	Expected Outcome
1. Monitoring nurses in documenting patient data using the RABET system.	Monitoring by direct observation for nurse performance using RABET system for completeness.	Head Nurses/Charge nurses	January 2024 and continuing	Nurses who need more training on the use RABET system for documentation are identified.

2. Ensure that nurses comply with complete documentation.	Auditing nursing staff completeness of documentation.	Head Nurses/Charge nurses	Continuing	Nurse documentation is complete.
3. Counsel nurses on the importance of complete documentation using the RABET system.	Orientation on the importance of documentation completeness using the RABET system.	Head nurses/Charge nurses	Continuing	Nurses can use the RABET system with ease and efficiency.
4. Send back non-compliant nurses to Education sessions on importance of nursing documentation completeness and train them on the use of RABET system.	Education sessions and training for RABET documentation	Clinical Research Nurses	Continuing (3-5 days per education session)	Nurses are retrained to produce accurate, timely and complete documentation.
5. Sustain complete nursing documentation.	Incentives; appreciation and certificates	Head nurses/Charge nurses	Continuing	Complete Nursing Documentation are sustained.
	Counselling for those who do not meet the required document completeness.			

3. Implementation

Nursing documentation uses electronic health records (RABET system) in entering data for each patient and this is the documentation-guiding framework. However, despite the availability of an automated documentation system, nursing documentation completion rate was not 100% and a subsequent memorandum was released directing all nurses to comply with documentation completion. This challenge was approached by multiple interventions, collectively coined *Nursing Documentation Completeness Project*. Nursing documentation audit was continuously conducted weekly from January up to July 2024, followed by a monthly meeting with all Head Nurses citing the full adherence of each staff. Per peripheral, there are two staff nurses who are covering the screening area for documentation. Two of the 16 peripherals offer 24hrs service (6 sessions), while the other peripherals offer three regular sessions. A verbal counselling letter was issued to the nursing staff who are neglecting to complete the documentation process. The non-compliant nurses are required to undergo education and training for three days. This project or

intervention strategy aimed to improve the documentation of nursing assessment in the patient record system as a way of quality improvement the nursing practice at Family and Community Medicine in all the PHC centers.

Results and Discussions

Nursing Documentation Completion Results before the introduction of NDCP

The data shown in Figure 1 represent the nurse documentation completion rate from January 2023 to December 2023. The lowest completion rate was recorded in January 2023 and June 2023 which is 76%. The highest completion rate was in December 2023 which is 89%. All completion rates were short of 100% expectation. The contributory factors which resulted in non-compliance to completion rates include the nurses’ lack of mastery of the use of the new system of documentation and understaffing. The findings were consistent with the results of the study conducted in Ethiopia [15] which highlighted understaffing and lack of training as factors affecting nursing documentation practices.

Figure 1: Nurse Documentation Completion Rate from January 2023 to December 2023

Figure 2: Nurse Documentation Completion Rate for January 2024 to July 2024

Nurse Documentation Completion After and Continuing Implementation of Intervention

Data in Figure 2 shows the nursing documentation completion rates from January 2024 to July 2024. The data shows an increasing completion rate from January 2024 to July 2024. Where the highest completion rate was recorded in July 2024, three months after the implementation of the intervention strategy. The high nursing documentation rate in July 2024 is attributed to

the continuous monitoring and auditing made by the head nurses or charge nurses and subsequent education and retraining of non-complying staff nurses. This result is supported by a study which showed that nurses who received thorough training in electronic documentation accomplish nursing documentation with ease and efficiency [16]. The nurse documentation completion rates from January to March 2024 were compared with those from

April to July 2024. The period from January to March 2024 marked the phase of designing the intervention, after the management issued a memorandum directing nursing documentation completeness on time. The action plan attempted to address the low completion rates in 2023. The implementation of the action plan or intervention strategy commenced in April 2024.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Nursing documentation completion rates improved across the PHC centers after the implementation of the intervention strategy. The improvement in completion rates is attributable to the Nursing Documentation Completeness Project which consists of continuous monitoring and auditing of documentation made by staff nurses, counseling, and education for non-compliant staff. The sustainability of the improved completion rates is ensured by incentive packages and certificates to recognize compliance with completion expectations and continuous counseling.

The completion rates of nursing documentation showed steady improvement, reaching a high of 96% by July 2024. However, the ideal target of 100% has yet to be achieved. This suggests the need for further action, such as intensify training programs and reinforcing the importance of timely documentation, particularly among nurses who remain non-compliant nurses or inconsistent from time to time. Addressing these gaps is vital to the achievement of full compliance and sustainability of complete and timely patient care documentation.

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